

THE PLACE AND ROLE OF SOCIAL INSTITUTIONS IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF SOCIETY

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Annotation: The article comprehensively analyzes the concept of social institutions, their theoretical foundations, their place and role in the development of society. The emergence, evolution and modern development trends of social institutions, as well as their functions in the organization and stabilization of society, are studied. The mechanisms of implementation of social institutions are studied using the example of Uzbekistan.

Keywords: social institution, society, norm, function, integration, legitimacy, social order, institutionalization, reform.

Introduction. Today, the place and role of social institutions in the development of society is one of the priority issues of fundamental importance. The sustainable development of society, its internal integration and adaptability largely depend on the strength and effectiveness of existing social institutions. For developing countries, including Uzbekistan, strengthening social institutions and adapting them to the requirements of the times has become one of the main directions of state policy.

The concept of "institution" (lat. institutum - "established", "order", "law") in a broad sense includes norms, rules and structures that regulate the life of society.

A social institution is a stable, historically formed, normatively approved form of social relations that arose in order to satisfy the social needs of society. Social institutions perform the function of regulating the behavior of people, directing their social activities and ensuring social order.

In sociology, there are various approaches and theories about the place and role of social institutions in the development of society. In particular: T. Parsons evaluates social institutions as a mechanism that ensures the functional stability of the social system. In his opinion, institutions coordinate human behavior and maintain social order (Parsons, 1951, p. 37). In this approach, social institutions are analyzed primarily as a means of stability and integration. Niklas Luhmann

approaches social institutions from the point of view of a communication system. In his opinion, modern society is a complex communication system, and institutions regulate the exchange of information and reduce social uncertainty (Luhmann, 1995, p. 143). Thus, Luhmann evaluates social institutions as a structure that ensures the stability of society through information and communication. Pierre Bourdieu emphasizes that institutions are not only a means of order and integration, but can also be a mechanism for producing social inequality (Bourdieu, 1986, p. 248).

For example, although an educational institution may seem to create equal opportunities for all, in reality it is likely to provide more opportunities for groups with social capital. From this point of view, he connects the effectiveness of social institutions with the concept of “social capital”. In his opinion, the stronger the mutual trust, cooperation and civic activity in society, the more effective social institutions will work (Putnam, 2000, p. 67).

A. Kholbekov interprets social institutions as a stable mechanism that regulates social relations in society, emphasizing their connection with national values (Kholbekov, 2014, p. 112). In his opinion, national traditions and the spiritual environment are an important basis for the stability of social institutions. F. Otamuratov analyzes the importance of social institutions in the process of modernization and focuses on the issue of transformation of national institutions in the context of globalization (Otamuratov, 2018, p. 84). In his opinion, a balance between traditional and modern institutions should be maintained in modern society. S. Shermukhamedov highlights the importance of spiritual values and educational institutions in the development of society. The scientist says that education is not only imparting knowledge, but also an institution that forms social responsibility and civic consciousness (Shermukhamedov, 2016, p. 56).

U. Begimkulov notes that the role of digital communications and media as a social institution is increasing in the conditions of the information society (Begimkulov, 2020, p. 73). This shows that the form and functions of social institutions are changing in accordance with the requirements of the times.

D. Rahimova evaluates the neighborhood institute as a national model of social integration and public control (Rahimova, 2019, p. 91). In his opinion, the neighborhood is important in increasing the social activity of citizens and solving social problems at the local level.

In the development of society, social institutions perform the following functions.

First, The integrative function unites people around common values, norms, and goals. Religious institutions integrate society through faith, state institutions through civic duty, and cultural institutions through the formation of national identity. This function plays a key role in ensuring the social cohesion of society.

Regulatory function

Each social institution regulates human behavior and creates the possibility of predicting it. Legal institutions direct behavior through norms and sanctions, economic institutions through market mechanisms, and the family institution through the socialization of the younger generation. The regulatory function ensures order and stability in society.

Socialization function

Social institutions prepare the new generation for society, teaching them collective norms, values, and behavioral patterns. Family, education, religion, and the media are the main agents of this function. Through the process of socialization, the cultural heritage of society is passed on from generation to generation.

Communicative function

Social institutions ensure communication and information exchange between people. Communication institutions based on modern media and digital technologies have become the main structures that unite all members of society. This function is especially strengthened in the context of globalization.

Types of social institutions family institute

The family is the oldest and most basic type of social institution. It is an agent of reproduction, child rearing, and socialization. The form and structure of the family have changed in different societies and historical periods - it is relative in nature.

6.2. State and political institutions

The state is the main social institution of modern society. It ensures state governance and legal order, protects public interests, and protects against external threats. In a broad sense, the system of political institutions includes parliament, the court, political parties, civil society organizations, and the electoral system.

6.3. Economic institutions

Property, market, money, banks, and enterprises form a system of economic institutions. They regulate the processes of production, distribution, and consumption of material wealth in society. The effectiveness of a market economy depends to a large extent on institutional factors such as property rights, contract enforcement mechanisms, and information infrastructure.

6.4. Educational institute

Education, as a social institution, fulfills the tasks of preparing the young generation for society, transferring knowledge and skills, ensuring social mobility and preserving the cultural heritage of society. For developing countries, reforming the educational institution and establishing a competitive system is crucial as a public investment in human capital.

6.5. Religious and cultural institutions

Religious institutions — churches, mosques, synagogues, and other religious organizations — shape moral norms and transcendental worldviews. Cultural institutions - theater, library, museums, press - form the cultural life of society. These institutions form the basis of cultural identity and social cohesion.

6.6. Legal and judicial institutions

The legal system, the prosecutor's office, the court, the bar - all of these constitute a complex of legal institutions. They perform the functions of implementing legal norms, resolving disputes, and protecting civil rights. The principle of the rule of law, as the basis of modern statehood, relies on the independence and effectiveness of these institutions.

Modern trends and implementation mechanisms of social institutions

7.1. Digitalization and institutional transformation

21st century digital technologies are fundamentally changing the way social institutions work. E-government services make the interaction of state institutions with citizens more efficient, transparent and convenient. As part of the Digital Uzbekistan Strategy, implemented in Uzbekistan since 2018, large-scale reforms are being carried out to digitize public services.

Digital transformation is transforming not only state institutions, but also educational, medical, banking and media institutions. Distance education, telemedicine and digital financial services are eliminating traditional institutional boundaries and are leading to the emergence of new hybrid institutional forms.

7.2. Globalization and the collapse of national institutions

The process of globalization is increasing the economic, political and cultural influence on national social institutions. International institutions such as the IMF, the World Bank, and the UN can influence the policies and institutional structures of nation states. At the same time, the issue of preserving national identity and ensuring institutional sovereignty has become one of the main political contradictions in the context of globalization.

7.3. Institutional reforms and implementation mechanisms

Reforming social institutions is a complex process that is not limited to formal changes - adopting laws, creating new organizations. Most importantly, informal institutions - cultural norms, traditions, and trust relationships - also need to change. As North noted, formal rules can be changed overnight, but informal norms are formed over centuries and change slowly.

In Uzbekistan, as part of the renewal strategy launched in 2017, the reform of social institutions is being implemented in several areas: the independence and effectiveness of the judicial system; reforming local self-government institutions - the mahalla system; modernization of educational and medical institutions; anti-corruption and improving the institution of public service.

7.4. Social capital and institutional effectiveness

Recent research has shown that social capital—trust, norms, and networks—is closely linked to institutional effectiveness. Robert Putnam (1993) has shown in his study of Italian regions that institutions function more effectively in societies with high levels of social capital.⁹ Thus, institutional reforms need to be accompanied by the development of civil society, the strengthening of mutual trust, and the accumulation of social capital.

7.5. Legitimacy of social institutions

The three types of legitimacy identified by Max Weber—traditional, charismatic, and rational-legal—are still relevant in explaining the stability of modern social institutions. In modern democratic societies, the legitimacy of social institutions largely depends on transparency, public control and participation, accountability, and the ability to adapt to the needs of citizens.

Conclusion. Social institutions are the skeleton and nervous system of society - they internally structure society, regulate people's relationships, and make collective life possible. The theoretical approaches considered in this article - functionalism, conflict theory, institutionalism, phenomenology, and rational choice theory - each shed light on certain aspects of social institutions and complement each other.

Social institutions are not a static feature of society, but dynamic structures that are constantly developing and changing. The processes of globalization, digitalization, and social change in the modern world are also deeply transforming social institutions. Responding to these changes, adopting innovative solutions while preserving the traditional institutional foundation

is one of the main tasks of today's state and society.

The issue of strengthening and reforming social institutions is of particular relevance for Uzbekistan. Cooperation between the state and civil society, institutional transparency, the rule of law, and making social institutions more effective through digital transformation are the main factors in the development of society.

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